

Experimentally exploring the effect of hydrogen addition on the DAIDT behaviour of n-decane

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Abstract

One of the challenges of Constant-volume combustion (CVC) is avoiding unwanted transitions to detonation. In the combustion mode of deflagration to autoignition to detonation transition (DAIDT), the coupling of the heat release from the autoignition wave with the local pressure wave can reinforce the pressure wave and develop into a detonation. This present study aims at experimentally exploring how the addition of hydrogen to n-decane affects its DAIDT behaviour. Experiments were performed at an initial pressure of 3 bar and for n-decane and hydrogen mixtures with 0 %, 5% and 10 % hydrogen by mass. The assigned initial temperature was 428 K which corresponded to a mean chamber temperature of 445 K and the one-zone cartridge heating resulted in a temperature gradient in the combustion chamber. It was found that with 10% hydrogen addition, no detonation was observed. The addition of hydrogen led to a higher temperature and pressure attained before autoignition occurred and a faster deflagration speed. Simulations found that the addition of hydrogen in a mixture increased the gamma value and constant pressure specific heat and therefore increased the ignition delay time at a given temperature and pressure. This combination of effects meant the flame had propagated further down the chamber when autoignition occurred and therefore autoignition happened closer to the chamber floor. An explanation for the detonation suppression at 10% hydrogen was that the temperature gradient in the remaining fresh gas combined with the proximity to the chamber floor meant the autoignition wave did not have enough time for enough of the heat release to feed into the local pressure wave to develop into a detonation.

1 Introduction

Constant-volume combustion (CVC) is an emerging technology with the potential to reduce fuel consumption in aircraft and propulsion systems. One of the challenges which needs to be overcome to further this technology is unwanted transitions to detonation. An unwanted detonation in CVC applications could seriously damage the system's mechanical structure and must therefore be avoided.

The combustion mode studied in this present work is deflagration to auto-ignition to detonation transition (DAIDT). When there is a reactivity gradient in a fully premixed fuel-oxidizer mixture, sequential autoignition of neighboring pockets of gas along this temperature gradient leads to an autoignition wave. Zeldovich et al. [1] concluded that the autoignition wave speed is inversely proportional to the gradient of ignition delay time, see Eq. (1).

$$u_a = \frac{dx}{d\tau_i} = \frac{dx}{dT} * \frac{dT}{d\tau_i} \quad (1)$$

Where u_a is the autoignition wave speed, τ_i is the ignition delay time, x is the spatial co-ordinate and T is the temperature. This equation assumes a negligible heat transfer between the pockets. As seen from

equation 1, a larger spatial temperature gradient ($\frac{dT}{dx}$) corresponds to a lower autoignition wave speed. The transition from autoignition to detonation has been explained by the Shockwave Amplification by Coherent Energy Release (SWACER) mechanism proposed by Lee et al. [2]. This mechanism states that autoignition in a confined space generates a pressure wave which moves into the unignited gas. If the autoignition wave propagates at a speed such that the heat release is in phase with the pressure wave running ahead, the pressure wave is amplified and this pairing can lead to a detonation. Bradley et al. concluded that aside from the proximity of the autoignition wave speed to the pressure wave, the mixture has to also be sufficiently reactive [3] for a detonation to occur. Bradley et al. [3][4] developed a parameter to quantify mixture reactivity for hotspot autoignition as the ratio of the time the pressure wave passed through the hotspot and the time of heat release duration. This parameter indicates that the amount of time the autoignition heat release has to feed into the pressure wave is an important factor in detonation development.

The DAIDT transition can be explored experimentally due to the phenomenon of a tulip flame. Ponizy et al. [5] found that when there is a flame propagating through a closed tube, due to hydrodynamic processes a tulip flame is formed. A tulip flame has a flame front with an inverted curvature as seen in figure 1 and the fresh gas in this curvature can be considered to experience conditions similar to adiabatic compression.

Figure 1. Example of tulip flame evolution [8]

N-decane is a single component kerosene surrogate and when exploring n-decane's DAIDT behavior experimentally, Quintens et al. [6] concluded that the transition between autoignition and detonation was due to acceleration of the autoignition wave front towards the speed of sound in the unburnt gas. The group of authors determined that the tulip flame is followed by a cool flame and a main heat release flame. Quintens et al. [7] also found that the compression history of the gas played a key role in detonation onset and therefore must be considered.

Hydrogen is an attractive fuel for the future because it can be produced carbon free and has clean emissions. Hydrogen is also considered to have the potential to be a major part of the future of propulsion [13]. However, developing a fully hydrogen combustion powered aeronautic propulsion system still represents a high technological challenge, therefore the use of hydrogen addition to a conventional kerosene can be investigated as a first step towards the decarbonation of air transports. In this respect, hydrogen's DAIDT characteristics need to be understood. This present study aims to explore how hydrogen addition to n-decane affects its DAIDT behavior. This will act as a starting point to understanding hydrogen's DAIDT behavior.

2 Methods

2.1: Experimental set up

For the present work, the deflagration autoignition detonation (DAID) experimental set-up was used as shown in figure 2. This set-up consists of a square inner section combustion chamber with dimensions of $172 \times 40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^3$. Located at the top wall of the chamber is spark plug with a transistorized coil igniter and an energy discharge of around 30 millijoules. A heating cartridge with a one-zone PID controller is used to heat the fresh gases inside the combustion chamber. The visualization area consists of two $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ quartz windows situated at the bottom of the combustion chamber. During the combustion processes, the chamber pressure is recorded by a piezoelectric pressure sensor (Kistler 6125CU20) located at the bottom of the combustion chamber at a frequency of 12.5 MHz. A highspeed camera (Shimatzu HPV2) is used to record schlieren images through the quartz windows with an exposure time of 159 ns and a recording rate of 80000 frames per second.

Figure 2. DAID experimental configuration

The one-zone cartridge heating results in a non-uniform temperature distribution along the height of the combustion chamber. An assigned temperature of 428 K was used for the experiments in this present study. The temperature distribution along the combustion chamber at different assigned temperatures was verified by [8] and the results are displayed in figure 3a. As seen, at an assigned temperature of 428 K, there is a temperature gradient in the chamber.

In this present work, the n-decane and hydrogen are mixed with an O₂/Ar mixture with respective molar fractions of 0.21/0.79. During an experiment, the chamber is initially filled with the combustible mixture which is kept at a fully gaseous state. The spark plug ignites a propagating deflagration. This deflagration propagates until a tulip flame is formed as shown in figure 3b. Due to the presence of both (i) higher temperature levels and (ii) a temperature gradient in the end-gas, an autoignition wave propagates through the fresh gas inside the tulip flame. The combustion regimes which follow are monitored by the schlieren imaging system. In addition, the pressure evolution is recorded by an oscilloscope connected to a piezoelectric 6125CU20 Kistler transducer and its Kistler 5011 charge amplifier. For more details about the experimental protocol, sensors and acquisition system, please refer to [8].

Figure 3. A.) Temperature profile inside of the chamber [8], B.) Example of a tulip flame observed through schlieren images

2.2: Numerical simulations

The initial chamber temperature and the chamber pressures during combustion processes are known, however the chamber temperature during combustion processes must be estimated through 0-D simulations. The simulation programs used in the present work include:

1. A 0-D constant volume combustor used to simulate a mixture's temperature evolution during autoignition and the ignition delay time under adiabatic conditions.
2. A 0-D variable volume combustor where the experimental pressure evolution is applied to the gas in the simulation under adiabatic conditions and the corresponding temperature evolution and volume reduction is calculated. This program therefore considers the mixture's compression history when determining ignition delay time [12].

Both codes were developed using the Cantera toolbox in Python.

Three n-decane air mechanisms with argon were considered, these included

- The Basevich mechanism [9], a reduced scheme consisting of 1082 reversible reactions and 111 species
- The Polimi mechanism [10], a reduced scheme consisting of 5741 reversible reactions and 231 species
- The Livermore mechanism [11], a detailed scheme consisting of 15787 reversible reactions and 2115 species

In experiments, pressures exceeding 16 bar were reached before autoignition occurred in the fresh gases, therefore using the constant volume combustor program, the ignition delay times for a stoichiometric n-decane-air mixture at 16 bar and a range of temperatures were simulated as shown in figure 4. It was found in [8] that the Livermore mechanism performed well when compared to experimental data, therefore this mechanism was used as a reference point. The results from the Polimi mechanism are closer to those from the detailed Livermore mechanism. The Polimi reaction is also far less computationally rigorous therefore, the Polimi mechanism was chosen for the simulations in the present work.

Figure 4. A plot of ignition delay time against $1000/T$ for a stoichiometric mixture of n-decane and synthetic air ($0.21 \text{ O}_2 + 0.79 \text{ Ar}$) at an initial pressure of 16 bar in a 0-dimensional constant volume combustor.

3 Results and discussion

To explore the effects of hydrogen addition on the DAIDT behaviour of n-decane, 3 sets of experiments were performed at an initial pressure of 3 bar and an assigned temperature of 428 K which corresponded to a mean chamber pressure of 445 K as seen in figure 3a. Three different proportions of hydrogen were explored: pure n-decane, and approximately 5% and 10% by mass of hydrogen. The liquid n-decane was first injected and vaporized into the chamber placed under vacuum whilst hydrogen was added in a second step in gaseous form mixed with the O_2/Ar mixture. Due to slight experimental variances in the amount of fuel and gaseous mixture injected, the equivalence ratio and proportion of hydrogen in the

mixture varied in each experiment. Table 1 summarizes the calculated conditions for the experiments involved in this study.

Table 1. Table of conditions for experiments performed in this study

Experiment number	% Hydrogen (molar)	% Hydrogen (mass)	equivalence ratio	Detonation observed
1123	88,58	9,90	1,01	No detonation
1124	88,82	10,12	0,99	No detonation
1125	88,66	9,97	1,00	No detonation
1126	88,81	10,10	0,99	No detonation
1127	88,90	10,19	0,98	No detonation
1128	88,71	10,02	1,00	No detonation
1129	79,08	5,08	0,98	detonation
1130	78,48	4,91	1,01	detonation
1131	78,24	4,85	1,02	detonation
1132	78,19	4,83	1,03	detonation
1133	78,01	4,78	1,04	detonation
1134	78,26	4,85	1,02	detonation
1135			1,00	detonation
1136			0,99	detonation
1137			0,98	detonation
1138			0,99	detonation
1139			1,00	detonation
1140			1,06	detonation

In the following discussion, time is taken relative to the spark plug ignition.

3.1: Effect of hydrogen on the autoignition delay

The first appearance of an autoignition wave during an experiment is considered as the autoignition delay time. This value should not be confused with the ignition delay values obtained at constant pressure conditions. The autoignition wave can clearly be identified in schlieren images by the appearance of a more distinct boundary between the burnt gas and fresh gas when compared to a deflagration as shown in figure 5.

To ensure the identification of the autoignition delay time between experiments was consistent, the following method was developed:

- 1.) Each schlieren image was subtracted from the neighbouring image.
- 2.) For the subtracted image, a threshold pixel value was applied such that any pixel with a value below that threshold was assigned a value of 0 (black) and any pixel with a value above that threshold was assigned a value of 255 (white).
- 3.) The start of autoignition was defined by the two following criteria:
 - The proportion of white pixels in the image were above a prescribed value
 - The position of the white pixels started propagating

An example of the image processing for the autoignition delay time determination is shown in figure 6.

Figure 5. Schlieren images demonstrating the difference in the boundaries between fresh and burnt gases for a deflagration wave and an autoignition wave

Figure 6. The image processing procedure used to determine the onset of autoignition

Figure 7. The mean autoignition delay time for mixtures with different amounts of hydrogen (by mass) for a mixture initially at 3 bar and 445K (assigned temperature of 428 K)

The mean autoignition delay time for each set of experiments is shown in figure 7. The addition of hydrogen decreases the autoignition delay time. The position of the deflagration wave at the onset of autoignition for each experiment is shown in figure 8 for 1 representative case from each set of experiments. As more hydrogen is added, the closer from the bottom of the chamber the deflagration has progressed at the onset of autoignition of the fresh gases.

Figure 8. Position of deflagration wave at the onset of autoignition for mixtures with different % of hydrogen (by mass)

3.2: Effect of hydrogen on deflagration and end-gas properties

The pressure evolution in the lead up to autoignition for a representative case for each set of experiments is shown in figure 9a. Also, the ignition delay times simulated in the constant volume combustor for the three mixtures is shown in figure 9b.

Figure 9. A.) Pressure evolution of experiments with different amounts of hydrogen (by mass) leading up to autoignition (exp 127, exp 132 and exp 140 respectively). Dashed lines represent the autoignition delay time. B.) Ignition delay time against $1000/T$ for an initial pressure of 16 bar

The addition of hydrogen increases the deflagration flame speed (as seen by the faster compression in the experiments with increased hydrogen in figure 9a) and increases the pressure attained at the point of autoignition. This explains the shorter overall autoignition delay time as hydrogen is added. However, as seen from figure 9b, the addition of hydrogen increases the ignition delay time for a given temperature and pressure. This can be explained by table 2, which shows that the addition of hydrogen increases the mixture's specific heat. The increase in deflagration speed combined with the relatively longer ignition delay time explains why the deflagration wave has travelled further in the chamber at the point of autoignition as more hydrogen is added.

Table 2. Table of simulated specific heats for the mixtures of n-decane with different proportions of air (0.21 O₂ + 0.79 Ar) at the initial conditions of 3 bar and 445 K

Experiment number	% Hydrogen (mass)	Equivalence ratio	C _p (J/K)	C _v (J/K)	γ
1127	10.19	0.98	720.12	492.18	1.46
1132	4.83	1.03	702.70	483.74	1.45
1140	0	1.06	682.27	473.09	1.44

3.3: Effect of hydrogen on the compressed temperature gradient

Simulations were run using the 0-D variable volume combustor where each point in the initial temperature profile shown in figure 3a was compressed using the experimental pressure evolution. Each point is compressed until reaching the experimental pressure at which autoignition was observed. Isentropic compression was assumed and the simulated decrease in volume ratio was applied to the domain position to estimate the height of the compressed temperature profile (1D compression hypothesis). Moreover, the domain position of the burnt gas boundary was determined to see how much of the compressed profile was within the fresh gas pocket.

Figure 10 shows the compressed temperature profile for mixtures with different proportions of hydrogen. Increasing hydrogen content increases the temperatures attained during compression and the magnitude of the spatial temperature gradient.

Figure 10. Plot of chamber location against temperature showing the compressed temperature profile for mixtures with different amounts of hydrogen (by mass). The dashed line represents the height of the visual window (e.g. how much of the compressed temperature profile there was optical access to)

3.3: Effect of hydrogen addition on detonation development

From Table 1, it is seen that in all the experiments with 10% hydrogen by mass, there was no detonation. Whilst for all experiments with 5% and 0% hydrogen by mass, a detonation was observed. The addition of hydrogen therefore pushes the regime away from detonation.

For the experiments with 5% and 0% hydrogen by mass, the time of detonation was determined by identifying the first frame in which a visible developing detonation was observed. Figure 11 shows the time and position of the autoignition wave in the frame just before detonation. The addition of hydrogen decreases the time of detonation appearance and increases the distance the autoignition wave has travelled in the chamber when the detonation appears.

To assess the effect of hydrogen addition on the autoignition speed, the ignition delay time for each point in the compressed temperature profile was simulated using the 0-D constant volume combustor. The results are plotted in figure 12. The flatter the line, the higher the value of $dx/d\tau_i$ (where τ_i is the ignition delay time and x is the domain position) and therefore the higher the autoignition wave speed. The addition of hydrogen increases the temperature gradient of the compressed profile and therefore leads to a higher autoignition wave speed. Nearer the bottom of the chamber, the $dx/d\tau_i$ value decreases and therefore the autoignition speed decreases, a finding in agreement with [6] obtained for pure n-decane. For the 10% hydrogen case, the deflagration wave progresses such that by the time autoignition occurs, only the part of the chamber with the lower autoignition speed is left for the autoignition wave to propagate into. For the 5% hydrogen and 0% hydrogen cases, the autoignition wave travels some distance before a detonation develops.

Figure 11. Position of autoignition wave and time in the frame just before detonation for mixtures of n-decane and air with different % of hydrogen (by mass) initially at 3 bar and 445 K (assigned 428K)

Figure 12. plot of domain position (taken relative to the top of the visualization window) against ignition delay time. Dashed lines demonstrate the position of the burnt gas boundary at 1.)when autoignition first begins and 2.) when detonation is observed.

According to the SWACER model, in the time between autoignition initiation and detonation, the heat release from the autoignition wave is feeding into the leading pressure which reinforces this pressure wave leading to a detonation. For the 10% Hydrogen case, the speed of the autoignition wave at the bottom part of the chamber is lower compared to the rest of the chamber leading to a slower heat release. Moreover, the proximity of the autoignition wave to the bottom of the chamber does not provide enough time for enough of the autoignition wave heat release to feed into the acoustic wave to develop into a detonation

4 Conclusions

Experiments were performed with n-decane and air with different proportions of hydrogen by mass initially at 3 bar and at an average chamber pressure of 445 K. For the experiments with 10% hydrogen, no detonation was observed. Therefore, it was found that the addition of hydrogen pushed the regime away from detonation for the given conditions. The addition of hydrogen led to the gas being compressed to a higher temperature and pressure before it auto-ignited and therefore led to shorter overall autoignition delay times. However, the addition of hydrogen also increased the deflagration speed and ignition delay time meaning the deflagration had propagated further down in

the chamber when autoignition occurred compared to cases with less hydrogen. This meant that as more hydrogen was added the autoignition wave started closer to the bottom of the chamber and therefore there was less fresh gas for the autoignition wave to propagate into. 0-dimension simulations were performed to find the compressed temperature gradient of the chamber and it was found that near the bottom of the chamber there was a larger temperature gradient translating to lower autoignition speeds. A possible explanation for the detonation suppression in the 10% hydrogen experiments is that the temperature gradient in the remaining fresh gas and the autoignition wave initiating so close to the bottom of the chamber meant the autoignition wave did not have enough time for enough of the heat release to feed into the local pressure wave to develop into a detonation.

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